

Planet RDC Program 3.2:

Machine Observation Data Processing Infrastructure (MODs)

Program Guidelines

The purpose of these guidelines is to provide potential project partners with the program strategy and intended outcomes, and clear guidance around expectations for projects.

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Revision History

Version	Date	Editor	Summary of changes
v0.1	18/03/2024	Jo Morris	Initial draft
v1.0	09/04/2024	Rob Clemens and Kerry Levett	Addition on workshop report, co-design guidelines and minor changes

Program Overview

The [Machine Observation Data Processing Infrastructure \(MODs\) program](#) will support the establishment of national shared infrastructure, services and standards to enable processing and reuse of automated observation and sensor data. The focus initially for this program will be on processing of imagery, acoustics and video data. National-scale infrastructure is needed to take advantage of, and manage, the large amount of data that are coming from deployments of camera traps, acoustic recorders and drones. These data need to be made analysis-ready to enable the vision of national-scale continuous monitoring.

In collaboration with research institutions, government, NGOs and other NRIs, this program will coordinate and align technical capability across multiple partners to enhance continental-scale observation. The data outputs will be made available in analysis-ready formats that are able to be easily integrated into environmental research infrastructures and repositories (e.g. TERN, IMOS, ALA, and those developed through MADSI). This will include implementation of persistent identifiers for observation data and associated instrumentation.

Building digital infrastructure to process machine observation data could include provisioning a combination of data storage, compute (cloud) resources, HPC, software tools for Extract Transform and Load (ETL), integration and visualisation, machine learning frameworks, data processing libraries, containerisation and orchestration, cybersecurity, documentation tools, and data governance frameworks.

Australia has many excellent producers of data and models. However, there is currently no whole-of-system approach to overcome the challenges of discovering and accessing data and models, assuring their reliability, and the cost-effectiveness of making them interoperable.

To ensure reliability and reproducibility, processing pipelines and their outputs need to be FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable).

The program will have a focus on reusable infrastructure and repeatable processes enabling MODs to be enabled for other machine observation data processing pipelines more rapidly and effectively. Technological solutions to enable data upload, AI processing, data management, data access, data storage, compute infrastructure, and citizen science will be developed collaboratively across the projects, facilitated by the ARDC. ARDC will provide technical expertise and underlying storage and compute infrastructure as appropriate.

Projects in the MODs program will collaborate with each other, and project outputs will be published and shared for reuse.

Other Planet RDC Focus Areas will provide input into the MODs program, and data and pipelines will be made available to researchers via Planet RDC infrastructure.

Program Outcomes

ARDC will deliver value to research, government and industry through the MODs program through:

- National data infrastructure supporting effective continental-scale environmental monitoring using cross sector, multidisciplinary data collaborations & leadership at the national scale.
- Uptake of agreed (inter)national standards or best practices for data, metadata, vocabularies, data exchange, quality, provenance, etc for machine observation data
- New methods of data processing (e.g., AI/ML) available to machine observation data
- Reusable infrastructure for the secure processing of camera trap, acoustic and drone imagery data to allow MOD pipelines to be more easily established for other machine observation modalities
- Enhanced interoperability of data across domains/disciplines/sectors
- Strengthening the quality and quantity of available data for research
- Research translation to government and industry to support evidence-based decision making
- Agreed methods to ensure the reliability and trustworthiness of data
- Reliable data and data processing pipelines that form the building blocks for the assessment of cumulative impact, environmental economic accounting, the nature repair market, accurate environmental prediction and trend reporting.

Project requirements

- Infrastructure developed or enhanced during the project is enduring and sustainable after the end of the project
- Existing standards, infrastructure and other resources are expected to be adopted or adapted where possible
- Infrastructure should be available and useful nationally
- Projects will use the [SAFE guide](#) to support a common view of the capabilities in the MODs program, to ensure better alignment of effort and interoperability
- Project teams will actively share and collaborate with other MODs projects including sharing of outputs, knowledge, communications and infrastructure when relevant

In Scope Activities

A project to deliver Machine Observation Data Processing Infrastructure will likely include the following activities:

- Clearly align to the strategic roadmap as defined in the [National Shared Machine Observation Data Processing Infrastructure Workshop report](#).
- Establishing a MODS partnership with stakeholders, through workshops and meetings leading to formal agreements
- Defining and implementing the management structure required to operate the MODs platform and products
- Projects to provide or improve the information products, e.g.
 - Implementing agreed collection protocols, data and metadata standards, vocabularies, identifiers, etc
 - Processing MODs data for reuse in modelling, analytics and decision support infrastructure (MADSI)
 - Building (or enhancing existing) and operating digital infrastructure(s) to enable the MODs
- Defining and implementing data governance appropriately
- Collaborating with other MODs projects, and reporting on activities and experiences to inform a repeatable architectures for developing a MODS processing pipeline that can be used across MOD modalities
- Other activities as co-designed by ARDC and project stakeholders

Out of Scope Activities

ARDC cannot invest directly in the following:

- Sampling or surveying to fill data gaps
- Provision/purchase/deployment of camera trap, acoustic or drone devices

Process and Timeline

The Planet RDC is following a community [co-design process](#) to deliver its programs.

2022

National consultation and policy analysis identified major national stakeholders and national priorities (see the [Planet RDC Program Description](#)). Through ARDC's 2022 national consultation and policy analysis we identified major national stakeholders and national priorities. Further consultations with the community have identified data from drones, camera traps and ecoacoustics recorders to be the focus of data challenges for this program.

2023

Commence program planning and consultation.

2024

Q1: Project shaping and planning stage - we will hold workshops and meetings with potential delivery partners and stakeholders to identify and select potential solution(s) and finalise the project team(s). Work with identified project partners to develop an investable project plan. A co-design workshop with over 50 stakeholders was held in February 2024 in Brisbane, in partnership with TERN and QUT ([read the report](#)).

Q2: Contract projects.

Q3: Commence projects.

Investment and Duration

The total ARDC budget for the MODs program is \$1.75m.

ARDC policy requires a minimum of 1:1 co-investment ratio between ARDC’s investment and that of all the other project participants combined. See the [ARDC’s Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details.

ARDC expectations for the conduct of co-investment projects

- Project partners will match ARDC co-investment at a minimum 1:1 ratio. Both cash and in-kind co-investment are acceptable. All co-investments must be made in an auditable form (see the [ARDC’s Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details).

- Projects must be aligned with the [NCRIS 2023 Guidelines](#) and the Principles set out in the [NRI Roadmap](#) (pg 14 pdf, pg 21 doc).
- Projects must have a dedicated project manager with appropriate experience and capacity. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the naming of a specific Technical Lead and Research Lead.
- Projects must have an ARDC-agreed governance structure to ensure desired outcomes are met. This may require a program-wide steering committee (including members not directly involved in the delivery of the projects) with defined Terms of Reference that meets at least quarterly. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the formation of a user reference group.
- Projects are required to commit to monthly traffic light reporting and other reporting requirements specified at contracting.
- Project plans must include the tracking of desired outcomes, including measuring the uptake of infrastructure by the research community, industry and government with clear KPIs that evidence the value to research, government and industry.
- Project plans should include user testing of ideas and prototype outputs early and often throughout project delivery.
- Most outputs will require ongoing operation beyond the life of the project in order to realise the intended benefits. Project plans must include a statement of the minimum ongoing maintenance likely to be required (both duration and resources) and a plan for that maintenance (to be agreed between ARDC and the project partners).
- Project outputs (including software) should be made as FAIR as possible, and the infrastructure developed should make research outputs FAIR for reuse and reproducibility. See the [ARDC guideline for FAIR data](#), [FAIR for Research Software](#), and [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments](#).
- Project teams are expected to collaborate across the Planet RDC and other ARDC-supported projects, as relevant and directed by the ARDC, to meet program objectives.
- Project teams are expected to attend and contribute to relevant ARDC workshops and events.
- Project teams are expected to engage in communication activities to raise awareness of their project and attract a growing user base within the earth and environmental sciences community. When doing so, projects need to acknowledge ARDC and NCRIS using the wording [provided by ARDC](#).